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ANALYZING EFFECTIVENESS OF FINANCIAL INCLUSION DRIVES IN KOTTAYAM DISTRICT (KERALA) WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO WOMEN MNREGA BENEFICIARIES

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ABSTRACT

The MGNREGA has mandated payments through formal financial institutions, it is expected to have resulted in enhanced financial inclusion of poor and marginalized sections of the society. Achieving inclusive growth makes financial inclusion a key policy concern for a developing nation like India. Linking Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme (MNREGA) with financial inclusion drive in Kerala posed to bring in large number of women population through their no frills savings accounts into the banking system and enable them to avail basic financial services like savings and credit. This paper attempts to assess the effectiveness of the process of implementation of financial inclusion drive for women's at the ground level in Kottayam district (Kerala) to identify any gaps and analyze its effectiveness in influencing financial behavior of women MNREGA beneficiaries so as to make future policies in this regard more effective. It was analyzed that women in semi-urban and urban areas have much higher clarity motives behind financial inclusion.

Keywords: Financial inclusion, No-Frills Accounts, Inclusive Growth

1. Introduction

The financial inclusion, with a focus on rural areas, has been one of Reserve Bank of India's main priorities since 2005. The RBI's plan includes provision of banking services to habitations with a population of 2000 and above, as per 2001 census, by March 2012. With this end in mind, in November 2005, the RBI asked banks to offer a basic banking 'no-frills' account with low or zero minimum balance and minimum charges to expand the outreach of such accounts to the low income groups. As of 2009, there were 3.3 crore no-frills accounts. The Business Correspondent (BC) model was launched, among other things, in order to extend the reach of banks to remote areas.

Despite a much focused expansion of branches in the rural and semi-urban areas, banks have not been able to reach out to the poor farm households in rural areas as the coverage is 39 percent against 60 percent in urban areas. Out of the 600,000 habitations in the country, only about 30,000, or just 5 per cent, have a commercial bank branch. Realizing the gravity of the problem, RBI in its Mid-Term Review of Monetary Policy (2005-06), urged the banks to scale up their efforts towards financial inclusion by promulgating a drive for financial inclusion at the district level (Agrawal et.al. 2009).

Process of Implementing Financial Inclusion Drive

Brief summary of the implementation of the financial inclusion drive in Kottayam district based on the information collected from the headquarters of leading Regional Rural Bank in Kottayam, i.e., by personally

interviewing its top officials concerned with implementation of the drive, other bank branch managers and Lead District Manager (LDM) at LDO (Lead District office), Kottayam.

As per the official data collected from Lead District Office, Kottayam (in June, 2015) regarding the "Progress under financial inclusion as on 25 March, 2012", 22,0057 no frills accounts were opened by all banks operating in the district although it has been declared 100% financially included on 29th March 2014 in special DCC (District Consultative Committee). Further, financial inclusion drive was linked to MNREGA scheme by opening no frills accounts for MNREGA workers for disbursement of their wages through these accounts.

2. Significance of the study

The definition of financial inclusion given by Dr Rangarajan Committee is now commonly accepted as the norm. Broadly financial inclusion occurs when an individual avails an array of financial services viz. receipt of transfer payments, savings (besides balance in the savings account, recurring deposits and fixed deposits), loans, insurance, short term credit (e.g. credit card, over draft) and remittance. Obviously, therefore, having a savings account is only a starting point for financial inclusion. Several studies have gone into the aspect of financial inclusion from the stand point of usage and constructed detailed indices to measure financial inclusion. Most of these studies have found that many of the 'no-frills' account have remained just savings accounts with account holders not accessing any other financial service from the banks. Since 2006, RBI has promulgated a targeted drive for financial inclusion throughout the country in every state, whereby state lead banks through SLBC (State level bankers committee) had to ensure participation of every unbanked household at the district-level via no frills savings accounts for at least one member from the same. So the main policy backdrop for the study is financial inclusion drive in Kottayam District in the state of Kerala.

3. Objectives of the Study

Given the above policy developments, it is both timely and pertinent to examine the issues as outlined in following objectives of the study.

- i. To make an assessment of the process of implementing financial inclusion drive in Kottayam district with respect to MNREGA beneficiaries in different geographical categories of rural, semi-urban and urban areas.
- ii. To determine the usefulness of linking social security schemes like MNREGA and financial inclusion drive by analyzing the effective usage of no frills accounts opened under MNREGA for savings, making deposits and availing credit, etc.
- iii. To identify gaps in relation to implementation of the financial inclusion drive at the ground level so as to bring it to the notice of various stakeholders involved in its execution such as policymakers, state governments and banks, etc.
- iv. To examine the level of awareness of targeted beneficiaries under sample regarding the drive, no frills accounts, perceptions about bank officials, etc., as well, as to identify the barriers hindering their access to banks, etc.

4. Review of Literature

Raihanath and Pavithran (2015) Financial Inclusion should not be seen as a social responsibility of the Governments and the banking system, but it is a potentially viable business proposition today which provides the poor with opportunities to build savings make investments and get credit.

Shivani (2015) in her research paper "Financial Inclusion In India" has concluded that in achieving inclusive growth in India, Financial Inclusion will play a vital role and help the nation to drive away not only rural poverty but also urban poverty in India. It is the duty of every Indian citizen to ensure that all the Indians will have a bank account and everybody should take part actively in achieving 100% financial inclusion in India.

Atul Raman (2015) in his research paper "Financial Inclusion and Growth of Indian Banking System" has explained the opportunities, scope and challenges for financial inclusion and concluded that Financial inclusion

plays a major role in driving away poverty from the country and a day will come when all Indians have their bank accounts and everybody will take part in financial inclusion

Vasanth et al (2015), said financial inclusion means connecting all individuals, who are in the remote rural areas, to a well -functioning financial system. This includes Easy accessibility of banking products and services, availability of cheap credit through appropriately designed loans for poor & low income households and small entrepreneurs and availability of basic financial products like insurance. However, given the current global crises, the need to scale-up Financial Inclusion is now perhaps more important as a complementary and incremental approach to work towards meeting the MDGs than at any other time in recent history.

Beta. Y, et.al.(2014) Based on the secondary and primary data findings, it is recommended for the central bank to urgently create lending programs for the un-bankable as additional funds/capital are urgently required to run their business. The central bank should cooperate with commercial banks to create products as needed by the poor's. The issue of branchless banking should be more considered as the household from the Susenas data indicate that most household own cell phones and sufficiently computer literate.

Agarwal and Garg (2014) Financial inclusion stands for delivery of appropriate financial services at an affordable cost, on timely basis to vulnerable groups such as low income groups and weaker section who lack access to even the most basic banking services. In this paper, the researcher attempts to understand financial inclusion and its importance for overall development of society and Nation's economy.

Vasanth et al (2013), Financial inclusion is emerging as a main concern for policymakers and regulators, which is a major driving force to achieve self sustained inclusive economic growth. Achieving the objective of hundred percent financial inclusions is one of the biggest challenges for financial sector. Financial Inclusion, broadly defined, refers to universal access to a wide range of financial services at a reasonable cost. These include not only banking products but also other financial services such as insurance and equity products

Srikanth .R (2013) Stated that Access to a well-functioning financial system, by creating equal opportunities, enables economically and socially excluded people to integrate better into the economy and actively contribute to development and protects themselves against economic shocks. The problem of financial inclusion addresses the involuntarily excluded as they are the ones who, despite needing financial services, do not have access to them

Rai and Saha (2010) view financial inclusion as a two step process with opening no-frills accounts as being step one and actual usage of the accounts as being step two. They take the case of Karnataka and develop a tool to measure the usage of the no-frills accounts using an Operationalisation index. Computing the operationalization index is important because although all 29 districts in Karnataka have been declared as financially included, in reality most accounts have remained inoperative. Reasons cited for this include distance from bank branch, illiteracy, absence of passbooks and lack of interest of the customers.

Adhikari and Bhatia (2010) examined another aspect of linking financial inclusion with social security schemes like MNREGA in the form of various fall outs of the above mentioned model emphasizing mainly on correlation involved even in MNREGA wage payments through bank accounts. The article explained the reality as it happened in some districts evidenced through findings from previous surveys and social audits in Orissa as well as in Deogarh (Jharkhand) which have shown that even wage payments through banks are not free of the maladies of earlier systems: corruption, fraud and misconduct.

Ramji and Meenakshi (2009) study regarding the aspect of implementation of the financial inclusion drive promulgated by RBI in 2005-06 in different parts of the country, the first primary data based study has been conducted in Gulbarga district in Karnataka which was declared 100 per cent financially included in January 2007 .It seeks to assess the implementation of the financial inclusion drive and usage of banking services by households and to understand the processes behind financial inclusion. It studies whether access to accounts leads to their usage and/or influences financial behavior. The study found that 36% of the sample remained excluded from any kind of formal or semi-formal savings accounts. Further, bank accounts have been opened typically to receive government assistance, mostly under the National Rural Employment Guarantee Programme

(NREGP). Usage and awareness of the accounts remained low. It concluded that access to accounts does not often lead to usage.

Natu, et al (2008) explored another aspect i.e. linking financial inclusion with social security schemes and proposes a model for the same highlighting the possible benefits. The paper explores an innovative way of achieving financial inclusion not just in terms of access but in usage as well. The authors believed that the drive towards financial inclusion as defined by the RBI as a no-frills account for every individual who wants one will be more relevant to the beneficiaries if it is tied to schemes such as NREGP that ensures a reliable stream of income although for a limited period of time in a year. They proposed that a variety of services can then be provided to the beneficiaries once such a channel of linking financial inclusion with NREGP has been established.

5. Research methodology

In order to achieve the objectives of the study, primary data has been collected by conducting a field survey through a structured questionnaire which was developed and used before (Ramji, 2007) for a study conducted in Gulbarga district in Karnataka with some adaptations/modifications relevant for our study. In present study, it was administered on randomly selected 150 households (of MNREGA job cardholders) spread over different geographical areas of Kottayam district in rural, semi-urban and urban areas selected on the basis of convenience sampling method. Various field visits were made during several months starting from June 2016 for conducting the survey to achieve outlined objectives of the study.

Finally, 129 questionnaires consisting of about 100 questions each were finally filled up and used for the analysis under this study. The survey collected details on socio-economic aspects of households like religion, caste, education levels, wealth, employment and income, etc. and on various aspects regarding the financial inclusion drive (such as strategies adopted by the banks to create awareness about no-frills accounts, levels of awareness amongst the target sample, savings behavior, access to banks, etc.). Apart from it, inputs through personal interviews and discussions with some branch managers and LDM (Lead District Manager) in Kottayam district (Kerala Gramin Bank & SBT) have been used to gain an insight into the whole process of 'Financial Inclusion' (FI) drive and its effectiveness.

6. Limitations of the study

- i. Time limit for the study was not sufficient for conducting an extensive research.
- ii. The information collected from the respondents may be biased

7. Analysis and Discussion

After describing the process of financial inclusion drive, a brief profile of survey of women respondents in different categories of our sample i.e. rural, semi-urban and urban is presented in Table 1, showing descriptive statistics about various characteristics of respondents in our sample. The list of bank branches under various geographical categories particularly of Kerala Gramin banks which is the leading RRB operating through more than 100 branches in Kottayam district basically served as the basis of classification under each geographical category of the sample i.e. rural, semi-urban and urban. In Kottayam district, three villages were surveyed under the category of rural areas while two areas were selected under semi urban and one area adjoining a town was selected under urban category of the sample for collecting primary data.

As shown in table 1, respondents were predominantly Hindu religion not just in total sample but also under its various classifications, while Christians are predominant in just urban areas and Among Muslims the concentration was highest in. It is only in 96% households of our total sample from which at least one member was able to read and write and around 26-30% respondents never attended school in total as well as in different categories of sample. As per reported figures, more than three--fourths of the sample had their own land, but the size of land holdings was very small making it uneconomical for their own cultivation. That is why agricultural labor was found to be the main occupation across the sample for their means of livelihood apart from doing work under MNREGA scheme.

Table 1: Characteristics of Respondents in Total Sample: An Overview

Basis	% of Respondents			
	Total Sample	Rural	Semi-urban	Urban
Religion				
Hindu	48.8%	45.8%	52.9%	39.1%
Christian	36.4%	33.3%	29.4%	47.8%
Muslim	14.7%	20.8%	17.6%	13.0%
Caste category				
Scheduled caste	52.7%	60.4%	73.0%	23.1%
Scheduled tribe	0%	0%	0%	0%
Other backward classes(OBC)	31.8%	32.1%	27%	35.9%
General	15.5%	7.5%	0%	41.0%
Education				
% of respondents who reported having never attended school	3.03%	3.80%	2.70%	2.60%
% of HH in which at least 1 member can read and write	96.96%	96.20%	97.30%	97.40%
BPL status				
% of HH having BPL status	32%	26.4%	40.5%	30.8%
% of HH having APL status	68.8%	73.6%	59.5%	69.2%
Ownership of cultivable land				
% of HH having their own land	76.0%	56.6%	94.6%	84.6%
% of HH not having their own land	21.7%	37.7%	5.4%	15.4%
Sources of income				
Agriculture(own cultivation)	5.5%	11.3%	0%	2.6%
Agricultural labour	90.7%	81.1%	100%	94.9%
Casual labour	1.6%	3.8%	0%	2.6%

Source: Questionnaire, HH: Households, BPL: Below poverty line, APL: Above poverty line

Financial Inclusion Drive

This section briefly analyses some major aspects relating to proper implementation of the FI drive at ground level by examining issues like level of awareness about the drive and no frills accounts, sources of awareness and proper conduct of household survey, thereby highlighting some gaps. It further examines the no frills accounts which were opened during the drive, reasons for opening them, awareness regarding their features/benefits as discussed below.

Table 2: Awareness about Opening of No Frills Accounts

	Total Sample		Rural		Semi-urban		Urban	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Aware	119	92.2%	45	84.9%	36	97.3%	38	97.4%
Not Aware	5	3.9%	5	9.4%	0	0%	0	0%
Does not know	5	3.9%	2	5.7%	1	2.7%	1	2.6%
TOTAL	129		53		37		39	

As shown in table 2, an overwhelming response regarding the awareness about no frills accounts was gathered from a majority of respondents (more than 92%) in total sample and similarly across all its three categories as they reported that they were aware about opening of such no frills accounts but their major source of awareness regarding the financial inclusion drive is Panchayats not just in total sample (around 71%) as a whole but also in all its geographical classifications. Although the results are not surprising keeping in view the fact that our sample consists of MNREGA workers who were supposed to be aware about such accounts due to compulsory linking of FI drive with MNREGA scheme. Further, during informal discussions with some bank officials, they revealed about the use of some 'Voluntary Vahini Clubs' (VVCs) acting like NGOs, (IRVs) 'Individual Rural

Volunteers' and SHGs in spreading awareness about the drive and in opening of no-frills accounts (as discussed in the process of implementing FI drive). However, this did not come out through our survey findings as not a single respondent reported about it.

Table 3: Whether any survey was conducted for having a bank account before

	Total Sample		Rural		Semi-urban		Urban	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Was Conducted	1	0.8%	0	0%	1	2.7%	0	0%
Not Conducted	39	30.2%	21	39.6%	1	2.7%	17	43.6%
Does not know	89	69%	32	60.4%	34	93.6%	17	56.4%

Further, another major finding revealed through table 3 is that no household Survey was conducted to identify 'unbanked' households, as hardly 1% of respondents responded positively to this question. A majority of people either did not know about this survey being conducted or they completely denied it. Even though it was mandatory to conduct such household survey before the drive, no such effort seems to have been undertaken by banks as revealed through the data of our sample highlighting a serious gap in implementing FI drive in proper manner. Interestingly most of our sample (MNREGA beneficiaries) was aware about no-frills accounts but not about the survey being conducted in this regard. It may be due to the fact that since it is mandatory to disburse their wages under MNREGA through these accounts so they were informed by panchayat or Gram Sabha officials about such no-frills accounts just for getting their wages.

Table 4: Reasons for Opening Account

	Total Sample		Rural		Semi-urban		Urban	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
For saving money	121	25.7%	45	27.4%	37	26.1%	39	23.8%
For safekeeping	105	22.3%	40	24.4%	30	21.1%	35	21.3%
To request loan	51	10.9%	13	7.9%	13	9.2%	25	15.2%
For receiving remittances	9	1.9%	4	2.4%	2	1.4%	3	1.8%
To receive wages under MNREGA	117	24.9%	46	28.0%	36	25.4%	35	21.3%
To receive any other govt. payments	66	14.0%	15	9.1%	24	16.9%	27	16.5%

While analyzing the reasons given by those who opened their accounts after October 2007 for opening such accounts, it was found that receipt of payments under MNREGA and other Government schemes was predominant at nearly 40% of the total sample, other popular reasons mentioned being 'for saving' and 'safekeeping money' as shown in table 4. Interestingly, all these major reasons were reported by rural population more as compared to urban and semi-urban population. It means that they think that bank is a safe place to keep their savings but whether they actually used accounts for such purposes will be analyzed later through their 'savings/financial behavior' with respect to these accounts in our next section.

Further, on examining who helped to open these accounts, a majority of our total sample (about 64%) as well as all its three categories reported that either it was Gram Sabha or Gram panchayat official who helped them to get their accounts opened in a bank which is quite obvious given the fact that our sample consists of MNREGA beneficiaries. As reported by around half of our sample, it is these people who told them about the benefits of such accounts but mainly for getting payments of MNREGA or any other government scheme without stressing much on their role for savings. In this regard, the role of NGOs (Non-government Organizations) and government officials is visible in a very minute proportion only in rural areas but totally absent in semi-urban and urban areas as not even a single respondent told us that they were informed about such accounts by any bank official.

Table 5: Did any bank representative explain all features of bank account?

	Total Sample		Rural		Semi-urban		Urban	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Yes	1	0.8%	0	0%	1	2.7%	0	0%
No	125	96.9%	52	98.1%	36	97.3%	37	94.9%
Will not answer	3	2.3%	1	1.9%	0	0%	2	5.1%
Total	129		53		37		39	

Table 5 clearly shows that most of the sample (over 95%) along with its various categories reported that no bank official/representative explained them the basic features of a bank account (no frills account) that it can be opened with a zero or minimum balance. It shows the lack of interest and initiative of bank officials in spreading financial literacy especially in rural areas as here this response is found to be highest. This point becomes prominent on analyzing the balances maintained in the accounts opened under the drive as shown in Figure 1.

It was also found that, only 7 accounts (5.4%) out of 127 (excluding questionnaires left unanswered in this regard) accounts opened during the drive were reported to have opened with zero balance while a majority of accounts were opened with a balance ranging from Rs.0-500 although technically they were zero balance accounts. Further examining the reasons behind it we found that a few respondents were told by some of the bank officials to deposit Rs.100 or Rs.200 etc. as a token money to open these MNREGA accounts on the pretext of inculcating savings behavior in them which was also revealed during our informal discussion with some branch managers in this regard. It indicates that the basic features of no frills accounts were not fully clear to respondents due to failure of banks to explain them correctly resulting in implementing the drive inaccurately as it was meant for those unbanked and poor households who could not open their accounts due to the requirement of having a stipulated minimum balance. So the awareness regarding various features/benefits of no frills accounts was very low.

Savings/Financial Behavior

It is important to look at the accounts usage behavior of surveyed respondents in terms of savings. Making deposits and withdrawals and use of credit facilities, etc, only then we will be able to analyze the impact of financial inclusion drive on the financial lives of targeted (MNREGA) beneficiaries. So in this section we discuss their savings pattern in general and financial behavior in terms of accounts usage.

Discouragingly more than 90% across the entire sample reported that they do not save regularly citing their 'Insufficient income' as the prime reason behind it. More than three-fourth of the sample reported that savings are made at the time of harvest which is quite obvious due to agricultural labour being predominant occupation in the whole district. When we asked their reason for saving (to those who said that they saved but it is too little and irregular) most popular response given was to face the future which means to deal with uncertainties relating to health and unemployment in future. So we can see that people are aware of the importance of savings but they are unable to inculcate a regular savings behavior due to their small income.

Savings, Deposits and Withdrawals

Unsurprisingly a majority of respondents across the sample (over 90%) did not make regular deposits due to insufficient and irregular income. Informal conversations with some of the respondents revealed that they were not making any deposits because they thought that the amount should be big enough like more than 500 or so only then it is worth depositing or acceptable in a bank.

Also the maximum last deposited amount (as reported by around 28% of sample) ranges anywhere between 2200-500 while more than 60% of our sample reported that they never made any deposit obviously due to small income. Again the purpose behind financial inclusion drive does not seem to be achieved here as these newly opened accounts during the drive were not used for savings and making deposits.

Use of GCC/KCC

Most of the respondents over 91 % across the entire sample as well as in each of its categories did not have any GCC (General purpose Credit Card) or KCC (Kisan Credit Card) and even those who had either GCC or KCC, (about 4%) reported that these credit cards were not issued to them while opening their accounts. Moreover, in spite of the maximum credit allowed on GCC which is up to 225000, not even a single respondent has used this credit limit to the maximum extent which may be possible due to the fact that either they were not aware of this limit or they might be finding some other informal sources of finance to be more easier means of borrowing money as compared to banks even when there is higher interest rate. Further, while asking about the use of this credit card money they did not clearly mention the purpose for which they took this loan. So we can presume that firstly, the respondents were not fully aware about the issue of GCC/KCC with their accounts and secondly, about the maximum credit limit they can avail by the use of these cards and for what specific purposes (like KCC for agricultural and GCC for non-agricultural purposes), they had no knowledge. It means that they were not able to reap the benefits of the credit facility available in the form of these cards even after opening their accounts with the banks around one and a half year of FI drive

Access to the Bank

This section tries to look at the aspect of accessibility in terms of economy, ease and convenience with which people can reach a bank's nearest branch catering to a particular area. This particular issue is really very significant for achieving the goal of 100% financial inclusion in any district or state.

Most of our respondents (about 90%) in total sample as well as all under various classified areas visit their nearest bank branch almost in a month. This observation is in line with the previous discussion regarding withdrawals which they used to make monthly. It appears that they went to the bank just to receive their wages from MNREGA scheme which means that they visit the bank branch under compulsion to get their wages and not because of any other financial need which they also reported on asking why they do not visit bank more often.

Further while exploring other reasons impacting their access to banks, we calculated their average cost of travelling to nearest bank branch for each area as well as for the entire sample that came out to be around Rs.14 for the total sample as a whole. Surprisingly, the cost was found to be highest in urban areas about Rs.16 and lowest in semi-urban areas though the cost was high in rural areas as compared to semi-urban areas. Discouragingly nearly 73% or about three quarters of our sample reported that they lose a full working day while going to bank. Now we can say that this loss combined with quite a high cost of traveling are posing a sort of barrier in access to the bank economically.

8. Findings

- The study brings out some serious gaps in the proper execution of financial inclusion drive at ground level. But at the same time, it is to be noted that this study should not be taken as a complete and final evaluation of financial inclusion drive in Kottayam district and its results cannot be generalized for whole district because our sample under analysis consists of only MNREGA beneficiaries as it focuses Kerala on studying the process of financial inclusion and its impact on them.
- However, it makes an assessment of on-the-ground realities and the usefulness of the drive to target beneficiaries (here MNREGA workers) and provide evidence in this regard so that future policies/initiatives can be made more innovative and effective. Banks must take steps to ensure greater financial literacy particularly keeping in mind the interests of poor and illiterate excluded sections of society.
- It is necessary for the Govt. and policy-makers to focus more on providing them financial education regarding the benefits of having an account and training for using it properly, as lack of financial awareness and education has been found to be the foremost reason behind their low usage in terms of savings and deposits.

- They should promote the goal of financial literacy by setting up more counseling centers and help lines especially in rural and remote areas so that no frills account holders can use their accounts in an effective manner.
- There is a need for a greater involvement of NGOs, farmer clubs apart from panchayat officials and most importantly SHGs, as they can prove to be really very helpful in propagating the idea of financial inclusion by stressing upon the need to save due to their compulsory nature of savings.
- It is also important that all banks adopt the core banking solution (CBS) not only in all bank branches but also in branches of regional rural banks. Further, integrate them with efficient financial inclusion models enabled on the use of technology in the form of Biometric smart cards involving other handheld devices like mobile phones and rural ATMs, etc., especially in rural and remote areas to reduce transaction cost and to ensure easy access to banking services through branchless banking.
- As the study looks into the usage of accounts after implementation of the drive in the district of Kottayam, KERALA, it should be of particular interest to banks, policymakers and other stakeholders (like state and central Governments, public financial institutions such as NABARD and some microfinance institutions acting as a business correspondent for banks) involved in implementation of the drive particularly in the state of KERALA. They may gain some valuable insights into making financial inclusion not just a goal to be achieved on paper but in real spirit as well by paying attention to some of the problem areas identified in proper implementation of financial inclusion drive in its real sense. Only then it will enable them to achieve the goal of 'inclusive growth' as all excluded sections can become a part of formal financial system.

9. Conclusion

Real financial inclusion needs to be measured not just in terms of number of Women households having an account but also by the extent of awareness about various other banking products/services available with them and their effective usage. Therefore it becomes very crucial to give them (especially the first time clients of the bank) a very basic introduction of these accounts explaining their features and potential benefits to achieve financial inclusion in real terms. However, there seems no concerted effort to educate the target beneficiaries about the features of a bank account on the part of bank officials as most of the sample (over 95%) along with its various geographical categories reported that no bank official explained them features of a bank account (no frills accounts) at the time of opening their accounts under the drive. While the branch managers felt that the poor cannot save money due to their meager income and use the accounts for deposits, so it cannot be a profitable proposition for banks, the poor clients thought that bank accounts are meant for some "bigger" amount of savings as more our sample reported that they never made any deposit as they were unable to save due to small income. Hence once again, it was evident that insufficient income combined with lack of awareness resulted in low usage of such accounts. The data clearly sports the fact that merely providing the people especially the rural poor with no-frills savings accounts does not lead to their effective usage in terms of frequent deposits or savings if there is complete lack of financial literacy and other convenience and cost related barriers.

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